

Strategies for Correlating DB2 & CICS SMF Records to aid Problem Determination

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Abstract— Proactive problem prevention in association with quick remediation—even automated—can solve issues before they impact critical business applications. Systems are becoming smarter, using analytics to find out preferences and make real-time suggestions for remediation. Today's Performance Management solutions require variety of components to support this plethora of systems. SMF records of IBM Z systems plays a vital role in analysis of performance records from end to end transaction perspective.

IBM Z, SMF 101, SMF 110, Db2, CICS, Performance Analysis, CPU time, authorization ID. Etc.,

I. INTRODUCTION

Companies need an answer that keeps an eye fixed on critical z/OS metrics using intelligent and dynamic thresholds to attenuate false positives. Any basic solution must provide operators and administrators with real-time visibility into mainframe application performance and transaction flows. But an efficient solution should also help simplify mainframe performance management and increase the effective use of mainframe system resources. Proactive problem prevention in association with quick remediation—even automated—can solve issues before they impact critical business applications. Systems are becoming smarter, using analytics to find out preferences and make real-time suggestions for remediation. Today's Performance Management solutions require variety of components to support this plethora of systems. Transactions are often examined as they flow across distributed and mainframe environments to ascertain what nodes more easily are the sources of any performance impact. Hence, it becomes necessary to correlate Performance records from end to end perspective in different address spaces to create visibility in application performance and transaction flow of mainframe applications.

- System Management Facility (SMF)

IBM System Management Facility (SMF) is a component of IBM's z/OS for mainframe computers, providing a standardised method for writing out records of activity to a file (or data set to use a z/OS term). SMF provides full "instrumentation" of all

baseline activities running on that IBM mainframe operating system, including I/O, network activity, software usage, error conditions, processor utilization, etc., [1]

The DB2 instrumentation Facility Component provides a powerful trace facility that can be used to record DB2 data and events. Accounting trace types collect information related to an application program. Performance trace collects a lot of detailed information about any type of DB2 event. It is used to identify the causes of performance problems [4]. The DB2 accounting trace produces hundreds of valuable metrics that are contained within SMF 101 records. It includes Plan name, Authorization id, Connection id, Correlation id etc., Plan Deadlocks, timeouts, lock escalations suspensions etc., Package name, collection id, CPU time, Elapsed time and details of executed SQL.

System Management Facilities (SMF) record type 110 data is generated by CICS Transaction server for z/OS for monitoring region-wide transaction statistics, transaction-level statistics, and storage exceptions [5]. This data highlights potential problems in CICS system operation and can help you identify system constraints that affect the performance of online CICS transactions.

II. NEED FOR RELATION

Transaction from End-to-end perspective flows through various address spaces. Starting from Online transaction server (CICS) to Database (DB2). Because CICS and Db2 have different accounting needs, it is not always easy to match up Db2 accounting records and CICS performance class records [3].

Three issues while trying to correlate the CICS and Db2 accounting and performance records.

There is no one-to-one relationship between the CICS performance class records and the Db2 accounting records. A Db2 accounting record can contain information about one CICS transaction, multiple CICS transactions, or part of a CICS transaction.

The Db2 accounting records do not have a field that matches exactly with the corresponding CICS performance records.

This article helps to understand the following points

- Ways to configure DB2 accounting records and CICS performance Class records to achieve co-relation for better debugging and performance perspective.
- Strategies for identifying the Key attribute or parameter for mapping records between Db2 and CICS in different scenarios.

III. GOVERNING THE RELATION

Naturally, Db2 puts down its bookkeeping accounts at thread end, or at the sign on of another approval ID that is reusing the thread. This means that each Db2 accounting record for the thread can contain information about multiple CICS transactions. In addition, if different types of CICS transactions use the same transaction ID to access Db2, the Db2 accounting record can contain information about different types of CICS transactions.

Three ways to influence the relationship between Db2 accounting records and CICS performance class records, to deal with these issues

Design CICS applications so that each CICS transaction ID and Db2 authorization ID always represents the same piece of work, that consumes the same resources. This ensures that each Db2 accounting record contains either a single piece of work, or more than one occurrence of the same piece of work, and it will not contain different items. If such a Db2 accounting record contains multiple items because the items are identical divide the resources used equally between them. The drawback of this configuration is need for re-design the application for accounting purposes.

Avoid reusing threads. This ensures that the thread terminates, and Db2 writes an accounting record, after each task, so each Db2 accounting record represents a single task. However, by doing this, the drawback is loss in the significant performance advantages of thread reuse.

Configure Db2 to produce an accounting record each time a CICS task finishes using Db2 resources. This is achieved by configuration in DB2CONN or DB2ENTRY definition. Use ACCOUNTREC(TASK) option instead of ACCOUNT(UOW). It ensures that there is at least one identifiable Db2 accounting record for each task. In case of different type of transaction using the same transaction ID to access Db2, CICS passes it network protocol LU6.2 token id to Db2 to be included in the accounting record. Correlation can be done using this token with relevant CICS transaction. Using ACCOUNTREC(TASK) is generally the most practical and complete solution to control the relationship between Db2 accounting records and CICS performance class records. It carries an overhead for each transaction, but its usefulness for a accounting purposes normally outweighs this overhead.

IV. STRATEGIES FOR MAPPING

There isn't one ideal method of coordinating Db2 bookkeeping records and CICS execution class records. In a couple of cases, it very well may be difficult to make the coordinating right since transactions are being run simultaneously. Much of the time in any case, there are strategies that you can use to coordinate the two kinds of records with sensible precision.

The two main factors that determine what strategies to be used

- CICS Transaction ID: Identify if each CICS Transaction ID represents only one possible transaction path or different transaction paths share the same CICS transaction id.

- DB2 Accounting ID: Each DB2 Accounting record relates to one transaction or part of one transaction or more than one transaction.

These factors combine to create four typical scenarios that helps in matching Db2 accounting records and CICS performance class records. The Figure.1 represents strategies for matching the records in each case.

Strategy A

In this scenario, each Db2 bookkeeping record contains data identifying with a solitary, recognizable CICS transaction. On the off chance that the transaction got to Db2 assets more than once, Db2 may have made more than one bookkeeping record for it. Map the Db2 accounting records relating to the transaction, to the CICS performance record for the transaction.

CICS Performance record contains the CICS activities related to a transaction. Db2 accounting records that apply to this transaction can be identified by using any one of the data items.

The CICS LU6.2 token – Configuring ACCOUNTREC(TASK) or ACCOUNTREC(UOW) in the DB2ENTRY or DB2CONN, CICS passes its LU6.2 token to Db2 to be included in the Db2 trace records as in Table 1. (Highlighted in orange colour).

Figure 1. Strategies for matching the SMF records

The authorization ID field. The authorization ID that a CICS transaction uses is determined by the AUTHID or AUTHTYPE parameter in the DB2CONN or DB2ENTRY as in Table 1 (Highlighted in Yellow color).

The timestamp fields. The start and end time for the thread can help identify the CICS transactions that the Db2 accounting record covers as in Table 1. (Highlighted in blue color).

TABLE 1 STRATEGY A MAPPING

SMF 110 CICS Record Type									
LPAR SSID	TRAN ID	PROGRAM NAME	AUTH ID	CPU TIME	ELAPSED TIME	START TIME	END TIME	LU6.2 TOKEN ID	
SY51	CICS3	DFHCRQ	PPFACSR	0.4389	0.012345	09-02-2020 12:34:50:00	09-02-2020 12:34:51:00	6590876	
SY51	CICS4	SBQE	SMMD1008	0.5498	0.00234	09-02-2020 17:14:40:00	09-02-2020 17:14:40:30	9761237	
SY51	CICS4	SBQV	SMV01009	0.38546	0.00184	09-02-2020 18:30:30:00	09-02-2020 18:30:30:53	9807123	
SMF 102 Db2 Record Type									
LPAR SSID	AUTH ID	ESTIMATED TIME	CPU TIME	SUSPEND TIME	PLAN	TIMESTAMP	LU6.2 TOKEN ID		
SY51	DBSS1	PPFACSR	0.589501	0.024994	0.0013	DISTSERVER	09-02-2020 12:34:51:00	6590876	
SY51	DBSS1	W24AA01	0.38924	0.0017834	0	DISTSERVER	09-02-2020 17:14:40:30	9761237	
SY51	DBSS1	W24AB01	0.18527	0.0013612	0	DISTSERVER	09-02-2020 18:30:30:53	9807123	

Strategy B

In this scenario, each Db2 accounting record can contain information relating to more than one transaction, so matching each Db2 accounting record directly to the relevant CICS performance record is not possible. However, the types of transaction that are present in the Db2 accounting record can be identified, because each transaction ID only refers to one type of transaction.

If only one type of CICS transaction is present in a particular Db2 accounting record, then for accounting purposes, the resources consumed in Db2 can be split equally between each transaction. This is reasonable because the transactions are almost identical. The number of commits and backouts in the Db2 accounting record indicates the number of units of work covered in this record.

However, units of work in the same transaction might use a different thread, and so not be present in the same Db2 accounting record.

If two or more different types of CICS transaction are present in a particular Db2 accounting record as represented in Table 2 (Highlighted in Yellow color), the method of distributing the resources equally cannot be used. In this case, create model transactions by periodically measuring the amount of Db2 resources used by each type of CICS transaction. Take these measurements by temporarily disallowing thread reuse, and looking at the resulting Db2 accounting records, which contains information relating to only one transaction. Use these model transactions to map the resources to the transaction. But periodically validate the correctness of the model transactions.

TABLE 2 STRATEGY B MAPPING

SMF 110 CICS Record Type								
LPAR SSID	TRAN ID	PROGRAM NAME	AUTH ID	CPU TIME	ELAPSED TIME	START TIME	END TIME	SERVER CLASS
SYSL1	CICS3	DFHCRQ	W24AA01	0.4389	0.012345	09-02-2020 12:34:50:00	09-02-2020 12:34:51:00	A
SYSL1	CICS4	SBQE	SMM01008	0.5498	0.00234	09-02-2020 17:14:40:00	09-02-2020 17:14:40:30	A
SYSL1	CICS4	SBQV	SMV01009	0.38546	0.00184	09-02-2020 18:30:30:00	09-02-2020 18:30:30:53	B
SMF 102 Db2 Record Type								
LPAR SSID	AUTH ID	ESTIMATED TIME	CPU TIME	SUSPEND TIME	PLAN	TIMESTAMP	LU6.2 TOKEN ID	
SYSL1	DBSS1	W24AA01	1.164011	0.458053	0.0013	DISTSERVER	09-02-2020 18:30:30:53	

Strategy C

In this scenario, each Db2 accounting record contains information relating to a single CICS transaction, but because several types of transaction use the same transaction ID, identifying which type of transaction is shown by a particular Db2 accounting record is impossible.

Mapping a set of records for one instance of a transaction and then reuse those figures, as in Scenario A is not correct method. Mapping all the individual CICS performance records with their corresponding Db2 accounting records is mandate. Until then, what type of transaction is represented by each Db2 record is not predictable.

Map each of the Db2 accounting records to the relevant CICS performance record by using the data items

- The CICS LU6.2 token – Configuring ACCOUNTREC(TASK) or ACCOUNTREC(UOW) in the DB2ENTRY or DB2CONN, CICS passes its LU6.2 token to Db2 to be included in the Db2 trace records as in Table 3. (Highlighted in orange colour).

- The authorization ID field. The authorization ID that a CICS transaction uses is determined by the AUTHID or AUTHTYPE parameter in the DB2CONN or DB2ENTRY as in Table 3. (Highlighted in yellow colour).
- The timestamp fields. The start and end time for the thread can help identify the CICS transactions that the Db2 accounting record covers as in Table 3. (Highlighted in blue colour).

TABLE 3 STRATEGY C MAPPING

SMF 110 CICS Record Type									
LPAR SSID	TRAN ID	PROGRAM NAME	AUTH ID	CPU TIME	ELAPSED TIME	START TIME	END TIME	LU6.2 TOKEN ID	
SYSL1	CICS3	SBQE	DFHCRQ	W24AA01	0.4389	0.012345	09-02-2020 12:34:50:00	09-02-2020 12:34:51:00	6590876
SYSL1	CICS4	SBQE	SMM01008	W24AA01	0.5498	0.00234	09-02-2020 17:14:40:00	09-02-2020 17:14:40:30	9761237
SYSL1	CICS4	SBQE	SMV01009	W24AA01	0.38546	0.00184	09-02-2020 18:30:30:00	09-02-2020 18:30:30:53	9807123
SMF 102 Db2 Record Type									
LPAR SSID	AUTH ID	ESTIMATED TIME	CPU TIME	SUSPEND TIME	PLAN	TIMESTAMP	LU6.2 TOKEN ID		
SYSL1	DBSS1	W24AA01	0.589501	0.024994	0.0013	DISTSERVER	09-02-2020 12:34:51:00	6590876	
SYSL1	DBSS1	W24AA01	0.38924	0.0017834	0	DISTSERVER	09-02-2020 17:14:40:30	9761237	
SYSL1	DBSS1	W24AA01	0.18527	0.0013612	0	DISTSERVER	09-02-2020 18:30:30:53	9807123	

Strategy D

In this scenario, each Db2 accounting record can contain information relating to more than one transaction, and also cannot use the transaction IDs to identify which types of transaction are present in the accounting record.

The present circumstance is best kept away from because it is probably not going to have the option to coordinate records precisely. In this situation, the best solution is to create model transactions, as described for Scenario B. Next, find a custom way to mark the CICS performance records with an identifier that is unique to each transaction. For example, the user could supply information in a user field in the performance records that identifies the transaction being executed. Now this field can be used to identify which of the model transactions should be used for accounting in this case.

TABLE 4 STRATEGY D MAPPING

SMF 110 CICS Record Type									
LPAR SSID	TRAN ID	PROGRAM NAME	AUTH ID	CPU TIME	ELAPSED TIME	START TIME	END TIME	SERVER CLASS	
SYSL1	CICS3	SBQE	DFHCRQ	W24AA01	0.4389	0.012345	09-02-2020 12:34:50:00	09-02-2020 12:34:51:00	A
SYSL1	CICS4	SBQE	SMM01008	W24AA01	0.5498	0.00234	09-02-2020 17:14:40:00	09-02-2020 17:14:40:30	B
SYSL1	CICS4	SBQV	SMV01009	W24AA01	0.38546	0.00184	09-02-2020 18:30:30:00	09-02-2020 18:30:30:53	A
SYSL1	CICS4	SBQV	SMV01009	W24AA01	0.38546	0.00184	09-02-2020 18:30:30:00	09-02-2020 18:30:30:53	A
SMF 102 Db2 Record Type									
LPAR SSID	AUTH ID	ESTIMATED TIME	CPU TIME	SUSPEND TIME	PLAN	TIMESTAMP	LU6.2 TOKEN ID		
SYSL1	DBSS1	W24AA01	1.164011	0.458053	0.0013	DISTSERVER	09-02-2020 18:30:30:53		

V. CONCLUSION

During Performance analysis, mapping the Db2 accounting records and CICS performance class records becomes mandate. In case of accounting exact mapping or relating the record types are optional. There is no one ideal way of matching Db2 accounting records and CICS performance class records. In a few cases, it might be impossible to make the mapping correct, because CICS transaction IDs are being run concurrently. In most circumstances the strategies can be applied to map the two types of records with reasonable accuracy. But in complex cases the approach could be hybrid approach where more than one strategy has to be applied.

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